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The Use of Graphic Images of Airport Objects in Marketing Technologies

The implementation of creative ideas in shaping technological dominants contributes to the formation of a sustainable image of airport development. The latter is successfully utilized as one of the tools in marketing strategies for the development of airports and surrounding areas as components of tourist destinations. In particular, the practice of using graphic images of air traffic control towers as part of trademarks for airport goods and services has been studied.

According to official estimates, the direct damage caused by the military aggression of the Russian Federation during 2022–2024 amounts to 176 billion US dollars (170 billion euros). The most affected sectors are housing, transport, energy, trade, industry, and education [1]. As of December 31, 2024, the total cost of reconstruction and recovery in Ukraine is estimated at 524 billion US dollars (506 billion euros) over the next decade [1].

The introduction of martial law led to:

- The closure of Ukrainian airspace to civilian aircraft;
- The temporary suspension of airport operations;
- The suspension of the implementation of the National Transport Strategy, the State Target Program for the Development of Airports in Ukraine until 2023, etc.

Significant destruction of transport infrastructure, particularly in aviation, requires the development of new sustainable development strategies and programs, as well as aligning Ukrainian civil aviation restoration legislation with international standards [2].

Aviation transport is a highly competitive industry.

Therefore, there is a constant need for marketing campaigns, including branding and rebranding of airlines, airports, and other enterprises and organizations providing non-aviation services at airports [3].

The restoration of disrupted and destroyed aviation infrastructure also requires new marketing strategies aimed at:

- Recovering lost positions in the aviation market;
- Reducing the time to reach pre-pandemic aviation transport volumes;
- Being ready to handle post-pandemic aviation transport volumes;
- Restoring attention and trust from both current and potential customers, etc. [3].

The effectiveness of recent developments is crucial to the attractiveness of airports in terms of comfort and safety for those staying within their premises.

It is expected that the outcome will be the stability of the growth in aviation transport volumes, an increase in revenues from both aviation and non-aviation services, and other positive results.

Sustainable development also involves the appearance of new types of buildings and structures, as well as the acquisition of new functions by existing ones [4–6].

Part of the development is being transformed into a socio-cultural space, attractive for creative industries, generating opportunities for the identification of airports as components of tourist destinations [7].

Special attention is given to the reorganization of urban planning and architectural solutions for buildings and structures, transport schemes, innovative technologies for contactless passenger, cargo, and mail handling, and marketing research. Within these studies, the experiences and best practices of airport branding are being examined and disseminated.

There is an increasing practice of naming airports after political and public figures, as well as scientists and cultural figures, as a tool for historical and cultural branding to enhance their role as parts of tourist destinations [3, 7].

For example, the domestic practice includes international airports such as "Zhytomyr" named after S. P. Korolev, "Kyiv" named after Igor Sikorsky, and "Lviv" named after Danylo Halatsky.

The development of airport territories, their components, features, and characteristics can also be used as a branding tool [3, 7].

Research conducted between 2017 and 2025 has allowed for the following:

- Identification of the features of the architectural environment that contribute to the formation of a stable image of airport development. Special attention was paid to the components of the airport terminal complex [3, 5];
- Definition of typological characteristics of high-rise dominants, not only in airport development but also in the surrounding areas—air traffic control towers (ATCT) [3, 6];
- Study of the practice of using images of ATCTs as graphic representations within trademarks for airport goods and services—see Figure 1 [3];
- Identification of the reasons for the loss of ATCTs as a characteristic feature of the stable image of airport architectural environments [3];
- Assessment of the impact of ATCT images on general perceptions of domestic airports [3, 6].

a

b

Figure 1. Eof trademarks for airport goods and services, which include graphic images of air traffic control towers (ATCT) [3]:

a – Edinburgh International Airport, Scotland;

b – Dubai International Airport, UAE.

The images of modern ATC towers (ATCTs) are diverse and attractive—ranging from traditional to extravagant.

The dominance of these structures in height (up to 132,2 meters) requires special design approaches, including the search for creative architectural and artistic concepts, as well as consideration of urban planning, technological, structural, and engineering requirements [3, 6].

Therefore, each ATCT plays a crucial role as a distinctive landmark in shaping the established image not only of the airport's development but also of the surrounding areas.

Leading architects (Ieoh Ming Pei, Moshe Safdie, Zaha Hadid) and renowned architectural and design firms (Aecom/Pininfarina, ARUP, Fuksas, Grimshaw-Nordic, RMJM, 3Dreid, among others) are involved in the design of ATCTs.

Several ATCT projects have received awards in urban planning and architectural competitions [3].

At the same time, it is important to note that the renewal of airport development strategies may be accompanied by changes in the visual identity of their built environment, rebranding of names, and, as a result, the loss of established images in the graphic representations of airport trademarks and service logos (Lelystad Airport, Dubai International Airport) [3].

The research findings were used in the development of preliminary design proposals for new ATCT buildings for airports in Ukraine [6, 8, 9].

Conclusions

1. The reconstruction and restoration of Ukraine's aviation transport infrastructure, incorporating modern marketing technologies, will contribute to forming an associative link between memory content and spatial objects [3, 10].

2. A unique case in global airport operations, where the silhouette of the ATCT building damaged in 2014 became a symbol of the resilience of the human spirit during the anti-terrorist operation, could become part of a rebranding strategy for Donetsk International Airport [3].

3. A creative approach to the design and construction of new buildings and structures, particularly ATCTs, can transform them into a tool for branding or rebranding airports whose infrastructure has suffered damage.

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